

Title: Prime Generating Function: A Comprehensive Analysis of $f(p)$

Abstract: This paper introduces a novel prime-generating function $f(p) = (p-1)^{p-1} + p$, which has been discovered to yield prime numbers for each prime input p . The function's properties and behavior are systematically analyzed, starting with the smallest prime, $p=2$, and iteratively applying the function with each subsequent prime output serving as the input for the next iteration. Through this process, a conjecture is proposed and rigorously proven, demonstrating that the function reliably generates prime numbers for all prime inputs. This discovery holds significant implications for number theory, offering new insights into the distribution and behavior of prime numbers. Furthermore, the discovery of this prime-generating function underscores the potential for further exploration and application in mathematical research.

Introduction:

Prime numbers are those numbers which are indivisible by any number other than themselves and 1, have fascinated mathematicians with their enigmatic properties and fundamental role in number theory. The study of prime numbers encompasses a wide range of topics, ranging from their distribution and properties to their applications in cryptography and computing.

Throughout history, mathematicians such as ***Pierre de Fermat***, ***Leonhard Euler***, and ***Marin Mersenne*** have made significant contributions to prime number theory, exploring various formulas and generating functions. Their work laid the foundation for our understanding of prime numbers and paved the way for the discovery of new prime-generating functions like $f(p)$. By building upon the insights of these eminent mathematicians, we seek to further elucidate the properties of prime numbers and advance the field of number theory.

The objective of this paper is to investigate the behavior and properties of the $f(p)$ function, with a specific focus on its ability to generate prime numbers. We embark on a systematic exploration, beginning with the smallest prime number, $p=2$, and iteratively applying the function to subsequent prime outputs. Through a rigorous analysis and proof, we aim to establish the validity of a conjecture regarding the function's prime-generating capabilities.

Methodology:

- Begin with the smallest prime, $p=2$.
- Use the function $f(p) = (p-1)^{p-1} + p$, where p is prime number.
- The output of $f(p)$, will always come as a prime number.
- Iteratively use the output of $f(p)$ of each iteration, as the input for the next iteration.

Illustration:

1. For $p=2$ (starting with the smallest prime number):

$$f(2) = (2-1)^{2-1} + 2 = (1)^1 + 2 = 1 + 2 = \mathbf{3} \text{ (prime number)}$$

2. For $p=3$ (as the output of $f(2)$ is 3):

$$f(3) = (3-1)^{3-1} + 3 = (2)^2 + 3 = 4 + 3 = \mathbf{7} \text{ (prime number)}$$

3. For $p=7$ (as the output of $f(3)$ is 7):

$$f(7) = (7-1)^{7-1} + 7 = (6)^6 + 7 = 46656 + 7 = \mathbf{46663} \text{ (prime number)}$$

and so on.

Proof:

1. Base Case: $p=2$:

Let's start with the smallest prime number, $p=2$.

$$f(2) = (2-1)^{2-1} + 2 = (1)^1 + 2 = 1 + 2 = 3$$

Since 3 is prime, the base case holds true.

2. Inductive Hypothesis:

Assume that for some prime number $p = k$, where k is a prime number greater than 2, $f(k)$ yields a prime number.

3. Inductive Step:

Now, let's consider the next prime number $p = k+1$. Since, we've assumed that $f(k)$ yields a prime number, let's denote it as $q = f(k)$.

$$f(k+1) = ((k+1)-1)^{k+1-1} + (k+1) = k^k + (k+1)$$

Since k is prime and $q = f(k)$ is also prime by our inductive hypothesis, k and q are coprimes (they have no common factors other than 1).

As we know, k can divide k^k evenly. But k does not divide $k^k + (k+1)$ because adding $(k+1)$ disrupts complete divisibility by k . And k and $(k+1)$ are coprime, making the sum $k^k + (k+1)$ not divisible by k . Therefore, $f(k+1)$ is not divisible by k .

Additionally, $f(k+1)$ is clearly greater than k , so it cannot be 1 or k . Thus, $f(k+1)$ has no factors other than 1 and itself, making it prime.

Conclusion:

In this paper, we introduced and explored a novel prime-generating function $f(p) = (p-1)^{p-1} + p$. Starting from the smallest prime, $p=2$, we iteratively applied the function and observed that it consistently produced prime numbers as outputs. Through a rigorous analysis and proof, we validated the conjecture that the function $f(p)$ reliably generates primes for prime inputs. This discovery provides new insights into the properties and distribution of prime numbers, highlighting the function's potential significance in number theory. Future research can further investigate the implications and potential applications of this prime-generating function.

References:

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